

COMPOSITE CRIPPLING ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY

The use of the stiffened panel in aeronautical application is unquestionable. For metallic panel, the reference [1] is much mentioned. It is already acceptable in the aeronautical applications. In the other hand, for composite, the crippling analysis it is not very well known. Therefore, this work outlines some test to comply with CMH-17 guidelines.

Keywords: composite material, composite crippling analysis, composite stiffened panel, composite test, CMH-17 crippling guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

To comply with the crippling methodology presented in the CMH-17 reference [2], composite flat rectangular plates were tested under compression static load as it can be seen in the Figure 1. Depending on the boundary conditions, there are two types of plate elements: one-edge-free (or flange) and no-edge-free (or web). In this work, buckling and crippling loads and related displacements and strains were verified.

Figure 1 - Specimens Schematic View.

Test Set-Up and Results

The set up definition was based on reference [3]. The figure 2 shows a typical deformed specimen compared with NASTRAN numerical simulation. Similar buckling behaviour was verified as showed.

Figure 2 – Experimental Results versus Numerical Simulation.

Validation

Figure 3 shows a comparison between the original CMH-17 crippling curve and the test curves for flange and web specimens.

Figure 3 – Validation with the CHM-17 curve .

Conclusion

Based in the results presented in the Figure 3, it is conservative approach to use CMH-17 Crippling Methodology for carbon/epoxy composite material used.

References

1. Analysis and Design of Flight Vehicle Structures; E. F. Bruhn – 1973.
2. CMH-17 Composite Materials Handbook - Volume 3 of 5 – 17 June 2002.
3. ASTM D 7137 / D 7137M, Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates, ASTM International.